

Long-Term Expansion Planning for Decarbonization Routes in Brazil considering Hydrogen Storage

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Contents

Context

- Hydrogen is a strategic element for the decarbonization of the global energy matrix.

- Importance:

Carbon-free

Storage

**Flexibility
management**

- Brazil:

Investment in research

Technology development

Objective

Investigate the introduction of **hydrogen** as an alternative for **storage** in the Brazilian energy system.

Scenarios

Results

H2 Power Generation | Brazil

Source: Own authorship (2023).

Results

Source: Own authorship (2023).

Results

Total Annual Costs | Country Name

Source: Own authorship (2023).

Results

Source: Own authorship (2023).

Results

Source: Own authorship (2023).

Problems

Scenario 3

1. Excel does **not support** new storage technology;
2. In txt file is easier to make **mistakes**;
3. Generated results in the OSeMOSYS cloud were **erroneously converted** by clicSAND;
4. **Errors** occurred in Simulations through CMD;
5. Visualization dashboard template **does not support** storing results;
6. **Difficulty** in calibrating the parameters.

Problems

Source: Own authorship (2023).

Conclusions and policy insights

BAU

- Higher CO₂ emissions.

HDG

- It does not change emissions.

HGS

- Faile!

NZR

- Higher initial costs. **Inviability?**

Conclusions and policy insights

- **Future work:**
 - ✓ **Correct the errors** in Scenario 3;
 - ✓ **Update** technology and commodity **data**.

References

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Thank You!